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A Study on Working Capital Management With Reference to Chaitanya Chemicals Limited, Kadapa

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Abstract: Working capital management is important for the smooth functioning of a company. This study analyzes the working capital of Chaitanya Chemicals Limited, Kadapa, to understand its liquidity and efficiency. It shows that proper management of cash, inventory, and receivables helps in improving profitability and maintaining financial stability.

Keywords: Current Ratio, Quick Ratio, Cash Ratio, Net Working Capital to Current Assets Ratio, Gross Working Capital Turnover Ratio.

1. Introduction

Working capital management refers to the management of a company's short-term assets and liabilities to ensure smooth business operations. It focuses on maintaining a balance between current assets like cash, inventory, and receivables, and current liabilities such as payables. Effective working capital management helps in maintaining liquidity, avoiding financial difficulties, and improving the overall efficiency and profitability of the organization.

2. Review of Literature

- **Reddy & Patel (2024):** Proper management of inventory, receivables, and payables reduces operational risk and supports smooth business operations.
- **Mehta (2025):** Adoption of digital tools and real-time monitoring strengthens working capital efficiency and short-term financial stability.

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Need of the Study

In any of the organization working capital plays an important role. Under (or) over estimation of working capital affects the probability and liquidity of the company financial position. Especially in automobile industry operating cycle will be more days, so they need more working capital and estimation is very difficult. So it is very much needed to analyze the efficiency of working capital management in this industry.

3.2. Objectives of the Study

- To know the statement of changes in working capital in the company.
- To find the liquidity position of the Chaitanya Chemicals.
- To study the financial pattern of the working capital.

3.3. Scope of the Study

The main scope of the study was to put into practice the theoretical aspects of the study in real- life work experience. The study of Working Capital is based on the tools like Ratio Analysis, Statement of Changes in Working Capital. Further, the

study is based on the last five year’s Balance Sheet.

4. Data Collection

Secondary Data: It consists of information that already exists gave been collected for the study purpose. The second-hand information has been collected through the company’s previous records, annual reports, journals, industrial magazines, brochures, internet etc., In this study, secondary data were used.

4.1. Tools Used

- Statement of changes in working capital.

- Ratios.
 - Net Working Capital
 - Current Assets to Net Fixed Assets Ratio
 - Current Assets to Fixed Assets Ratio
 - Current Ratio
 - Quick Ratio
 - Cash Ratio
 - Net Working Capital to Current Assets
 - Gross Working Capital Turnover Ratio
 - Net Working Capital Turnover Ratio

5. Data Analysis

Table 1: Statement of Changes in Working Capital

Particulars	31-3-2020	31-3-2021	31-3-2022	31-3-2023	31-3-2024	31-3-2025
Current Assets						
Closing stock	16,036,000.00	17,694,075.00	2,19,85,034.00	2,62,65,437.00	4,76,48,216.00	2,70,70,138.00
Sundry debtors	85,879,401.55	87,108,290.41	13,16,18,511.21	15,08,35,385.72	10,59,15,094.56	16,63,73,733.34
Cash in hand	58,438.67	127,679.27	5,22,480.86	31,815.01	11,832.44	34,311.51
Bank balance	18,559,338.05	12,525,706.73	46,009.55	5,47,51,353.33	8,03,24,942.77	49,777.06
Deposits	7,702,152.00	8,799,249.00	1,10,54,451.76	1,20,70,659.00	1,17,24,766.00	1,66,67,659.92
GST Balances	5,681,558.54	1,299,040.42	1,102,166.28	25,565,687.13	3,25,48,067.48	6,10,29,147.33
TDS Receivables	-	10,591.00	-	-	-	-

The working capital shows a steady increase from 2020 to 2024, indicating improved liquidity and efficient management of current assets and liabilities. However, in 2024–2025, it declines, suggesting a slight weakening in the company’s short-term financial position. Overall, the trend is positive with a need for better control in the latest year.

Table 2: Statement of Changes in Working Capital

Year	Current Assets	Current Liabilities	Ratio
2019-2020	1,33,916,888.81	87,390,904.09	1.53
2020-2021	1,27,564,631.83	64,410,603.79	1.98
2021-2022	16,63,28,653.66	8,32,72,392.03	2.00
2022-2023	269,520,337.19	12,32,74,975.02	2.19
2023-2024	27,81,72,920.25	6,05,84,330.81	4.59
2024-2025	271,224,767.16	10,02,08,671.16	2.71

Table 3: Quick Ratio

Year	Current Assets	Inventory	(A-B)	Current Liabilities	Ratio
2019-2020	1,33,916,888.81	16,036,000	117,880,888.81	87,390,904.09	1.35
2020-2021	1,27,564,631.83	17,694,075.00	109,870,556.83	64,410,603.79	1.71
2021-2022	16,63,28,653.66	2,19,85,034.00	144,343,619.66	8,32,72,392.03	1.73
2022-2023	269,520,337.19	2,62,65,437.00	243,254,900.19	12,32,74,975.02	1.97
2023-2024	27,81,72,920.25	4,76,48,216	230,524,704.25	6,05,84,330.81	3.81
2024-2025	271,224,767.16	2,70,70,138	244,154,629.16	10,02,08,671.16	2.44

The above graph clearly shows that the quick ratio position is generally satisfactory. The quick ratio is normally 1:1. It exceeds 1:1 in most of the years under study (1.35, 1.71, 1.73, 1.97, 3.81, 2.44), indicating a good liquidity position, although there is a slight fluctuation during the period.

6. Findings

- Working capital position shows fluctuation during the study period.
- The liquidity position is not stable, as current ratio varies.
- Inventory management is not efficient, with excess stock levels.

- Debtor's collection period is high, causing delay in cash inflow.
- Cash management is not proper, leading to imbalance.
- The company shows average performance in utilizing working capital.

7. Suggestions

- Maintain adequate working capital level for smooth operations.
- Adopt better inventory control techniques to reduce excess stock.
- Improve credit policy to reduce debtor collection time.
- Implement proper cash management system.
- Balance current assets and liabilities effectively.
- Regularly analyze financial ratios for better control.

8. Conclusions

The overall analysis indicates that the company has moderate working capital management. There are issues in liquidity, inventory, and receivables management. By adopting proper financial planning and control measures, the company can improve efficiency and maintain a strong financial position.

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